

Data description for the reproducibility of the results

Manuscript Title

Magneto-Micropolar Control of Drag and Lift in Channel Flow Past Cylindrical Obstacles: Role of Eringen Number

Repository Contents

This draft contains the parameter settings used to generate the numerical results reported in the manuscript. All simulations were performed using the finite element method implemented in FreeFEM++. The source code is available on a reasonable request to the corresponding author at muhammad.sabeel@cust.edu.pk.

Parameter Values Used for Figures

Figures 4 - 12:

- $K = 0.1$
- $\alpha = 1$
- $\beta = 2$
- $M_s = 0.1$
- $Re = 500$
- $0.005 \leq Er \leq 0.1$

Figure 13 - 19

- $0.01 \leq K \leq 0.5$
- $\alpha = 1$
- $\beta = 2$
- $M_s = 0.1$
- $Re = 500$
- $Er = 0.1$

Figures 20 and 21:

- $0.005 \leq K \leq 0.1$
- $\alpha = 1$
- $\beta = 2$
- $M_s = 0.1$
- $Re = 500$
- $Er = 0.1$

Parameter Values Used for Tables

Table 2

- $300 \leq Re \leq 500$
- $0.01 \leq K \leq 0.1$
- $0.01 \leq Er \leq 0.1$
- $0.01 \leq M_s \leq 0.1$
- $1 \leq \alpha \leq 2$
- $2 \leq \beta \leq 3$

Software

All computations were performed using FreeFEM++ finite element software. The source code is available on a reasonable request to the corresponding author at muhammad.sabeel@cust.edu.pk.